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PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF INDIAN WOMEN

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Abstract

The U.N held a millennium summit in 2000 with a robust declaration for bringing about gender equality. The disparity between men and women in India is glaring for historical reasons evolved in stages through changed situations Socio-Economic Fields with greater emphasis on patriarchal in sowed rather than on metriarchical. However, the question before us is whether UN summit of 2000 took into consideration the Socio-Economic relations of India being subsequently led to the wider chasm/rupture between Indian women and men based on Socio-Religious and economic cords leading further is the denigration and denial of her right to life, dignity etc. These papers mainly focus on women's right and attempts to explore the possibilities of bringing uniformity in terms of rights and responsibilities though the women rights in India have evolved in the patriarchal style and hence have patriarchal orientation. Throughout this paper a solemn attempts has been made to discuss the challenges before that Indian women such as female feticide, dowry, trafficking, of girls and denial of their due rights. However, the objectives of the paper are what are the possibilities and practices that could revamp Indian society with gender being equal and secondly, the legal option and constitutional guarantees will be dealt with exploring the possibilities and prospects for Indian women to be equal to men.

Keywords: *Women's Rights, Gender equality, family, Empowerment, Challenges, Problems and Prospects.*

Introduction

The fight for women rights could be traced to 17th, 18th and 19th century, the seeds of fight for their sprouted there when the burgeoinsie democratic revaluation did not incorporate the concept of equality, since then the women as a distinct gender staged spectacular battle demanding vociferously the recognition for their rights and pleaded for being treated as human being. Women accomplish multifarious roles as a mother, wife, bread winner, and the care taker of family, recantation to this we have seen warier women like kitturu channamma, Rani janshi laxmi and belwadi mallamma who fought revolutionary against foreign rules to liberate

implications for girl child's innocence and formative years of her life and snatching the child's physically, mentally and emotional development, resulting in a high IMR." Child marriage takes away from a girl child the innocence of her formative years of life necessary for physical, emotional and psychological development. Spousal Rajasthan being a self-evident case in India.

Son as a major or potential component of a family: The strong pining for a son to be the bed-rack of Indian family resulted is dreadful damage to the women health. The proclivities for son emerged in family, components of Indian society only when the age old matriarchic family system was metamorphosed with the advent of feudal society characterised by land owning and division of it among the families the concept of private property took deep roots while embarking upon huge land as a prideful issue. With all this agriculture become the major occupation and the male's role got widely recognized. This entire historical process weakened ignominiously, the position of women causing nastily consequences upon women. Thus the formation of patriarchal social unit i.e., family with sole emphasis on male child as an embodiment of socio-economic, seriously rest utter in the utter-neglect of girl-child and women as insignificant entities. Today's phenomena of women being relegated (a trafficking position) has evolved throughout the historical (World) Process. The issues confronting the women in various aspects of human existence have become convoluted moorings across the historical evaluation of Indian social system, hence, divorcing them both physically and mentally.

Issue of feticide thought: The infant mortality rate is already high in India. The feticide rate is even higher than that, this signifies the lowering statues and sex-ratio of women in India. Amino centesis-technology appears to be lousing a greater damage to the women statues, which successfully defects the sex of fetus before its complete formation in the womb. Thus, the feticide the sex-selective abortion and the mal-mounishrent have often been spoiling, the proportional growth of women population in India. According to one estimate nearly 10 million female fetuses gets aborted, causing irreversible decline in women population in both Punjab and Haryana is 894 to 793 (1961-2011) and 910 to 820 (1961-2011) respectively. Despite the government lawful ban a pre-sex determination exercise, this practice has not yet been stopped and seem to be widely prevalent in north India. Moreover, these unethical practices have been consistency causing high death toll among women folk in India.

Education: Education is one of the most important areas of empowerment of women. Though the rights to education under Article 21 of the Indian Constitution have made it compulsory to

provide free education to everybody, unfortunately, it is still a redeemed object of women. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan to an extent has been successful in bringing the girl child back to the schools, yet their retention rate in the school is lower has been evident that there is a greater drop out of the girl students as they move up to the higher levels. The main reasons for this is that the parents expects girls to look after the siblings when they are at work, the parents are more in chinned boys education as against the girls as they feel that the girls are to be married off, increasing cost of education etc. Thus the universalisation of primary education in India remains a remote daydream for the women.

Forced evictions and exclusion: In India the widows are forced out of their matrimonial home to feed themselves along with children. On the statues of women the UN Special Reporter argues: “In almost all countries, whether ‘developed’ or ‘developing’, legal security of tenure for women is almost entirely dependent on the men they are associated with. Women headed households and women in general are far less secure than men. Very few women own land. A separated or divorced woman with no land and a family to care for often ends up in an urban slum, where her security of tenure is at best questionable”. “There is spread-eagled evidence, in India that, women spend more on basic family needs, and at the same time men spend a significant part on alcohol and tobacco, etc.

Sexual harassment and the workplace: The deliberation on sexual harassment of women in their workplace. The passage of the ‘Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition act) Bill 2013’ However the bill has not been translated into effective implementation. The provisions have not been invoked for social taboos associated with sexual harassment”. The women are discriminated against in respect of payment of remuneration for their work. Women entrepreneurs getting credits to start their still a for cry business.

Rape: There in India has been a unsteady increase in the numbers of rape cases in the last 12 years. According to National Crime Records Bureau, in 2012, 25000 rape cases were reported. In the rural areas, particularly in Northern India, the upper caste people involve in mass rapes to have power to subtle the members of the lower caste groups. The nasty and brutal gang rape in Delhi has precipetedly activated the Indian government to pass a stringent low by bringing an amendment to the criminal low to deal with rape cases rigorously.

The Prismatic Societal Attitude: over burdened by traditions and conventions having in themselves a built in conventional rape-spur fiber subject women to brutal rapes. Further, the social communities and religious communities also Lorca women into practicing conservative,

conviction rate. However, this proposal failed to garner support among the government and have been shelved.

The attainments of drastic reduction in the crime rate against women squarely demand the multi-layered co-ordination strategies across the compounded system. And also demand innovative co-coordinating mechanisms having integrated into those agencies that deal with women related crimes. Co-ordination between government, social society and even family should not be ignored. In 1956, the Indian government, through Hindu Succession Act sought to reform the women folk by legally allowing them the right to inheritance. Extension of both financial and emotional assistance from both formal and informal set ups shall entail the independent and secured life of a women. The Politico-economic assistance to the women would render them independent and educated and hence become aware of rights and of self-existence. It should be noted that a well-known feminist writer once said that the best possible way for women to be protected is to be covered with justice, this implies that giving woman a formal legal education is must for planting her into a permanently secured life.

The official organization like police that deals with the victimized women in India. Judges responsible for providing justice to women victim should be given special training to handle such cases consequently. Both police and judiciary should be inducted into formal training to make them imbibe the principle of justice underlying the term 'justice' and deal those cases (Specifically women cases) with utmost sensitivity. Those are all possible only when gender awareness or gender sensitization education is given in all schools, colleges and universities. If police and judiciary implement the law rigorously, the problems at least, partially get redressed. The women's organizations must try to empower men and women by transforming the attitudes of the society towards the suicidal traditional practices. One of the most important tasks of the women organizations and NGOs is to help women in rebuilding and restoring their lives and confidence. The goal can be realized only when the women are adequately educated about their legal rights and made them economically independent to take conscientious decisions of their own life. Counseling at various levels in the structural system also help women to be vibrant and enlightened life (victimized women).

Violence against women can be reduced with cultural norms and attitudes towards the women being changed change should be made in the school curriculum. That educates the students at the various levels on issues like human rights and gender issues. "Curriculum can work in eliminating the gender gap and lead to women equality in its entirety.

The violence against the women in India is perpetuated by the indigenous cultures. Therefore the indigenous communities must try to introduce mechanisms that eliminate such age old practices harmful to the women. Religious leaders and researchers must restructure the sacred manuscripts and doctrines to encourage egalitarianism society for women to be respected.

Conclusion

In short, the Millennium Development Goal on gender equality and women's empowerment can be ushered in India the following socio-economic evils which have strong cultural back up and the supportive cultural pulp needs to be quarantined to realize the goals of millennium the traditional the evil such as female infanticide, dowry deaths, honor killings, domestic violence, or sexual abuse is eliminated. The only strong stroke like summarily elimination could yield place for women empowerment a reality.

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